

APPENDIX 6 - QUESTIONNAIRE ON PERCEPTION OF UTILITY AND EASE OF USE – TAM

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EVALUATION OF PERCEPTION AND EASE OF USE – TAM

Part 1 - Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

1) Was it easy to LEARN how to use CPRP?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

2) Is it easy to REMEMBER how to use CPRP?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

3) Is the method for INTERACTING with the CPRP clear and understandable?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

4) Is CPRP FLEXIBLE enough to be used?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

5) Was it easy to GAIN skill in using CPRP?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

6) Do I find CPRP easy to use?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

Part 2 - Perceived Utility (PU)

7) Does using CPRP make studies faster in the activity of ELICITING and SPECIFYING requirements in accordance with the LGPD?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

8) Does using CPRP improve performance in the activity of ELICITING and SPECIFYING requirements in compliance with the LGPD?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

9) Does using CPRP increase productivity?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

10) Does using CPRP improve the effectiveness of eliciting and specifying requirements in compliance with the LGPD?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

11) Using CPRP makes my job easier.

- Strongly disagree

- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

12) Do I consider the CPRP useful for my work?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

Part 3 - Intention to Use (ITU)

13) Do I intend to use CPRP whenever possible?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

14) Do I intend to increase my use of CPRP?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

15) Would I adopt CPRP in the activity of ELICITING and SPECIFYING requirements in accordance with the LGPD in the future?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree somewhat
- Indifferent
- Strongly agree
- Strongly agree

Part 4 - Open Questions

16) After analyzing the CPRP, what are the main perceived benefits in relation to the catalog?

17) What are the main challenges identified after analyzing the CPRP?

18) Which aspects of CPRP would you consider easy/difficult to use in your day-to-day work at the Software Factory?

19) To what extent could the CPRP contribute to improving your activities related to privacy requirements?

20) How does CPRP fit (or not) into the processes and tools you already use in the Software Factory? Is there anything that would facilitate this integration?

21) What would make you use CPRP more often or recommend its use to other professionals at the Software Factory?

22) What suggestions would you give to make CPRP more useful, user-friendly, and applicable to real-world Software Factory projects?
